

A STUDY OF TECHNOLOGICAL ALLIANCE AND PERFORMANCE OF INDIGENOUS BAKERY INDUSTRY IN OSUN STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The paper examines the technological alliance and performance of indigenous bakery industry in Osun State, Nigeria. The primary data were collected using structured questionnaires from indigenous bakeries in three cities (Ile-Ife, Ilesa and Osogbo) of Osun State. The second stage of selection used snowball sampling techniques to select the owners or managers of 120 bakeries in the selected town. The data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The results show that 83.3% of the respondents engaged in alliances with people of related businesses. Many of the respondents (41.7%) had collaborations with a particular supplier of the raw materials they use in baking while the remaining had business arrangements with research institutes and sales agents. The result from the regression analysis shows that the value of R is 0.851 which is the correlation of the independent variable with the dependent variable. R Square ($R^2 = 0.724$) is the coefficient of determination. It means that about 72.4% of the variation in bakery performance can be explained by technology alliance. The Analysis of Variation (ANOVA) outcome with F value = 1.317, p-value = sig value = 0.026 which is less than 0.05 ($p < 0.05$), confirm the regression analysis result that technology alliance is significant to performance of bakery industry. The paper concludes that the indigenous bakeries in the study area entered into alliances with suppliers of raw materials, research institutes, people in related businesses and entities outside the supply chain and the alliances led to minimization of costs, maximization of outputs, efficient productions and increase in sales of the enterprises.

Keywords: *Technological alliance, Performance, Indigenous bakery, Industry*

1.0 Introduction

Bread is a staple food made from flour, water and other ingredients. It is an important staple food in many countries especially in Africa and Southeast Asia (Issaoui *et al.*, 2021). The Bakery industry in Nigeria is one of the key drivers of the economy. Nigeria consumes roughly 13 million tons of bread and bakery goods—about 56 kg per person annually, making it Africa’s largest consumer. Statista projects Nigeria’s bread market revenue at US \$18.8 billion in 2025—approximately \$79 per person. The market is expected to grow annually by 10.39% (CAGR 2025-2030) – Statista 2025. The industry creates jobs, as quite a number of people are employed by the industry. This includes those directly employed by the industry, the distributors and hawkers of bakery products. The National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) (2012) reported that Nigerians spent a total of ₦586.3 billion on bread between 2009 and 2010.

Technology plays very significant roles in the process of converting raw materials into finished products. It has been described as a systematic knowledge for the manufacture of products, the application of processes and rendering of services, including any integrally associated managerial and marketing techniques (Ilori, 2006). The implication of this definition is that technology adoption plays very significant roles in product innovation, development and acceptability. Acquisition of the appropriate technology enables the industry to operate effectively and efficiently (Efunwole, 2022). Participation in technology alliances is considered an increasingly important means to addressing the challenges firms face as a result of the reshaping of the competitive business environment due to globalization. Globalization ignites new technologies, markets, and industries and, thus, rapidly changes criteria for competitive advantage and firms survival (Barkema *et al.*, 2002).

The liabilities of newness and smallness perspective recognize that a small firm can increase its survival prospect through external relationships (Aldrich and Auster, 1986). One major reason for this is that alliances provide access to resources that would otherwise take years to build, thereby buffering a firm from the hazards of young age (Baum, Calabrese and Silverman, 2000). Relationships with prominent industry players can influence firms' activities and products (Powell, 1998). Evidence from the resource-based view suggests that a firm can benefit from resources beyond those it possesses (Teece, 1992) if it forms alliances.

In Nigeria, the growth of the bakery industry seems not to have kept pace with global trends. The quality of products offered by the bakeries in Nigeria have attracted attention (Ajayi and Olawale, 2007; Ojinaka, 2001; Ohimain, 2014; Efunwole, 2019). The bakery industry in Nigeria is bedevilled by a lot of challenges such as lack of developmental infrastructure, low strategic planning capability, poor access to finance and shortage of skilled manpower among others (Nigerian Industrial Revolution Plan (NIRP), 2014). As a result, only a negligible number of the bakeries are making their impact felt through the provision of satisfactory products and services to their customers. Many of the bakeries rarely survive their teething stage of development while some others already in the business gradually lose their market share and possibly fold up.

Literature has shown that concepts such as technology capabilities have been used to proffer solutions to the problems facing the bakery industry and results showed that bakeries are weak in investment and linkage capabilities. However, there is little evidence on the use of the Technology Alliance Model to study these challenges. A good number of the bakery owners are totally ignorant or deliberately ignore the necessity for technology alliance in the bakery industry. An understanding of technology alliance in the bread baking industry is important in order to determine appropriate interventions to strengthen the ability to respond to challenges and enhance production and innovation; hence, this study.

The paper examines the forms of technology alliances and assesses the effect of technology alliance on the performance of the bakery industry in the study area. The study was restricted to indigenous bakery firms producing bread in Ile-Ife, Ilesa and Osogbo, Osun State in Southwestern Nigeria. Limitations of this study relate to time, funds, logistic and human resource constraints which limited the area of coverage of the study.

2.0 Literature Review

Technology Alliance

Caloghirou, Hondroyiannis and Vonortas (2003) point out that inter-organizational collaboration and/or inter-organizational alliance is not a new phenomenon. New, however, is the dramatic growth of alliances during the past couple of decades (Mowery *et al.*, 1998; Narula and Hagedoorn, 1999; Hagedoorn, 2002; Sadowski and Duysters, 2008) and the attention alliances have attracted by managers, academics, and policy makers (Belderbos *et al.*, 2004; Fontana *et al.*, 2006; Okamuro, 2007). Furthermore, the nature of inter-organizational alliances has shifted not only regarding the organizational form (from equity to non-equity collaboration), but also regarding the motivation and function. Today, inter-organizational alliances not only address peripheral interests of firms but issues concerning firms' very core functions such as research and the development of new products and processes which have previously been kept strictly in-house (Narula and Hagedoorn, 1999; Caloghirou *et al.*, 2003). Technology alliances (also referred to as R&D partnerships) are defined as collaborative arrangements where two or more independent organizations share some of their R&D activities (Hagedoorn, 2002). These agreements encompass informal arrangements as well as formal arrangements and range from discrete, short-term contractual arm-length agreements – such as joint R&D pacts and joint development agreements – to equity-based joint ventures. Thus, technology alliances may vary considerably regarding the degree of inter-organizational interdependency and level of internalization depending on the different types of agreements (Hagedoorn, 2002).

The participation in technology alliances is considered an increasingly important strategic means to address the new challenges firms face resulting from the reshaping of the competitive business environment by globalization. Globalization ignites new technologies, markets, and industries and, thus, rapidly changes criteria for competitive advantage and firm survival. It shortens product life cycles by higher rates of technical obsolescence and accelerates the pace at which firms must develop new technologies, products, and processes to stay competitive and to survive (Barkema *et al.*, 2002). Added to this are the continuously increasing technology complexity caused by the inter-sectoral nature of new technologies, escalating R&D costs, and increasingly sophisticated customers (Brockhoff *et al.*, 1991; Mowery *et al.*, 1996). This intensely competitive environment makes innovation a risky business and decent returns of R&D investments difficult to attain. Many firms started to realize that the traditional focus on internal R&D activities may be insufficient (Brockhoff *et al.*, 1991). Thus, firms started to form technology alliances with other firms, government agencies, or universities as these are increasingly viewed as a vital option to maintain firms' long-term competitiveness and to ensure the survival of the firm (Bayona *et al.*, 2001). Consequently, the importance of technology alliances with customers and/or customer integration in the R&D process to help to define features and requirements of innovative products and processes and, by doing so, enhance the probability of market acceptance, has been recognized since at least the 1970s (Tether, 2002).

Collaboration with customers during the R&D process is considered to be important to reduce the risk associated with the market introduction of new products and/or processes. Not only may technology alliances with customers help to find the right balance between product features, quality, and price, they may also provide a deeper understanding about customer behaviour which may be important to identify requirements and important refinements. Furthermore, customers may provide complementary knowledge and technical know-how. If the customer is a well-known, respected member of its community, the technology alliance may also increase the chances that the innovation will be adopted by other firms from this community (Tether, 2002;

Belderbos *et al.*, 2004). Consequently, collaboration with customers may be especially important to ensure market acceptance and diffusion of innovations when the products and processes under development are more novel or complex or when the market needs are still only poorly defined (Tether, 2002; Belderbos *et al.*, 2004).

Technology alliances with suppliers share many features of customer alliances as both alliance types are in the same vertical relationship (Tether, 2002). However, supplier alliances have been widely examined in the context of firms' trend to focus on core competencies and the outsourcing of a high percentage of the value-added of firm products (Dess *et al.*, 1995). In fact, interest in the early involvement of suppliers in the research and development of new products and processes rose from the success, especially during the 1980s, of Japanese automobile and electronics firms as the performance gap between Western and Japanese firms has been associated amongst others to the close buyer-supplier relationships of Japanese firms (Tether, 2002). Thereby, technology alliances with suppliers are instrumental to reduce the lead time and development costs as well as to avoid costly downstream production problems and product quality improvements. In other words, technology alliances with suppliers are often related to firms' improved efficiency of research and development activities and process improvements aimed at further cost reductions and heightened product quality (Belderbos *et al.*, 2004; Aschoff and Schmidt, 2008).

Apart from technology alliances within the supply chain (i.e., customer and supplier alliances), firms can engage in co-operative arrangements for innovation with several other types of partner organizations beyond the supply chain (Tether, 2002). Alliances with universities, research institutes, research and technology organizations (Santoro and Gopalakrishnan, 2000; Santoro and Bierly, 2006), consultants (Kaufmann and Tödtling, 2001), and even with existing industry competitors (Dodgson, 1991) have all been advanced in this respect. Universities and public research institutes are widely considered to be important sources of new scientific and technological knowledge (Caloghirou *et al.*, 2001).

However, firm motives for forming technology alliances with competitors are complex and not necessarily (directly) anti-competitive (Fusfeld and Haklisch, 1985; Hamel *et al.*, 1989; Tether, 2002). Competitors may, for example, form alliances to acquire new skills from its alliance partners, build a better understanding of competitors' behaviour, and enhance their competitive position. Thus, there may be areas where the skills and capabilities of partially competing firms are complementary for developing new products and processes (Tether, 2002). Especially when these firms face other competitors or alliances that already have all the required skills and assets, it makes sense to pool their capabilities rather than undertake time-consuming and costly efforts to replicate the specific capabilities of the partner (Teece, 1992; Gomes-Casseres, 1994; Tether, 2002). Furthermore, alliances between competitors may be crucial to develop and promote technical standards as they allow firms to gain the critical mass and market power required to persuade more businesses to use their design (Teece, 1992; Gomes-Casseres, 1994). Firms may also enter competitor alliances to avoid investments, reduce financial risks, and obtain subsidies (Hamel *et al.*, 1989). Finally, cost reductions may motivate alliance formation between competitors. Competitors or firms from the same sector often have similar processes and, thus, might offer valuable input for the development of new or improved production processes (Aschoff and Schmidt, 2008). It is not surprising, therefore, that technology alliances are nowadays often regarded as a first-best option instead of merely being a last resort (Narula and Hagedoorn, 1999). Research indicates that, after only small growth during the 1960s and 1970s, the number of newly formed technology alliances has grown dramatically since the 1980.

Categories of Technology Alliances

Alliances take a variety of forms ranging from non-equity agreements associated with one way or two way licensing through to joint venture agreements, equity participation or consortium. (Caloghirou *et al.*, 2003). A firm's decision to form alliances is moulded by external forces rather than by the firm's managerial, technical and other resources. According to (Hagedoorn, 2002) alliance can be of three types namely:

- i. *Technology development alliances* – to enhance R&D capability of the firm to ensure its competitiveness on the rapidly evolving field of knowledge relevant to its focus.
- ii. *Commercialization alliances* – to provide firms with expanded manufacturing and marketing capabilities.
- iii. *Financial alliances* – to help provide the firm with the capital needed to support its technology acquisition and commercialization strategies'

Technology alliances can be vertical where the main purpose is to get access to a technological capability or horizontal where the main purpose is to secure access to a market. Technology alliances are likely to have an impact when industrial and commercial stages are reached. According to Sadowski and Duyster (2008), technology alliances are often established without the appropriate consideration of their impact on the long term overall competitiveness of the firm. There are varieties of reasons for corporations to engage in technology alliances. Reducing the cost of access to technology capabilities seems to be one of the major reasons. Also, saving the cost of the research effort has been considered to be a strong incentive to form an alliance.

3.0 Research Methods

Primary data were collected through structured questionnaires to generate relevant data on indigenous bakery firms and how technological collaborations affect business performance. The population for the study consists of indigenous bakeries in Osun State, Nigeria. A two-stage sampling technique was adopted for the study. The first stage involved purposively choosing three major cities in the state as the area where the respondents of the study were drawn. The reason for this was that the major producers of bread in the state were located in these cities. The second stage was the use of snowball sampling techniques to reach as many as possible owners/managers of indigenous bakeries available in the selected towns. So, a total of 120 owners/managers constituted the sample size of the study. The data collected were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics.

4.0 Results and Discussion

As in Table 1, the study revealed that most of the respondents were male (76.7%) and married (66.7%). Most of the respondents fell between the age bracket of 41 years and above.

Performance of the Bakery Industry

Table 2 measures the performance of the bakeries. Four items were used as shown in Table 2. The first item measured the present worth of the business and the result shows that about 27% of the respondents agreed that their business worth is very high, 57.5% agreed that their present worth is high, 13.3% agreed that their present worth is low, while 1.7% agreed that their present worth is

Table 1: Respondents' Socio-demographic Characteristics

Characteristics	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	92	76.7
Female	28	23.3
Marital status		
Single	27	22.5
Married	80	66.7
Divorced	12	10
Others	1	0.8
Age (years)		
21-30	18	15
31-40	47	39.2
41 and above	55	45.8
Highest educational qualification		
Primary school leaving certificate	3	2.5
Junior secondary school certificate	16	13.3
Senior secondary school certificate	49	40.8
B.Sc/HND and equivalents	44	36.7
Post graduate degree	8	6.7
Location of bakery		
Urban area	70	58.3
Rural area	33	27.5

Peri-urban area	17	14.2
Year of bakery establishment		
Less than 10years	28	23.3
10-15years	86	71.7
Above 15 years	6	5
Total	120	100

Table 2: Performance Profile of Bakeries

Performance	Very high n (%)	High n (%)	Low n (%)	Very low n (%)
The present worth of the business	33(27.5)	69(57.5)	16(13.3)	2(1.7)
Estimated asset at the beginning of business	2(1.7)	22(18.3)	67(55.8)	29(24.2)
Sales volume per day	54(45.0)	51(42.5)	12(10.0)	3(2.5)
Output level per day	46(38.3)	59(49.2)	12(10.0)	3(2.5)

Keys: n= frequency, %= percentage

very low. From the result, it was discovered that over 84% of the respondent's present worth is high which shows that the bakeries were performing well.

The second item which measured performance is the estimated asset at the inception of the business. Result shows that about 1.7% of the bakery owners estimated their assets to be very high at the beginning, 18% are of the opinion that they started business with high assets, while about 55% of the respondents agreed that their bakery business took off with low estimated assets. About 24% said they started business with very low business assets. The result shows that 79% of the respondents in the study area started with low estimated assets. This result reaffirmed one of the major characteristics of micro enterprises which is that they usually start with small capital usually below 5 million naira.

The third item measured the sales volume per day. By sales volume, the study found out the amount of output that the bakery was able to convert to cash and result from the field shows that 45% of the respondents said that the sales volume per day is very high and 42.5% agreed that their sales volume per day is high. Meanwhile, 10% of the bakery owners believed that their sales per day is low, while 2.5% agreed that their sales volume is very low. This result shows that 87.5% of the respondents are able to turn a higher unit of their output into cash on a daily basis and this can also be used to ascertain that the bakeries are performing well. This also affirms the conclusion of Odinaka (2013) that bread is one of the most consumed food items in homes, restaurants, and hotels with predominant consumption among the poor and young.

The fourth item is the output level per day which measures the rate of production, i.e. the amount of bread produced per day. In the field, it was discovered that not all the bread produced on a daily basis were made available for sale, some of the products were produced to cater for family consumption, staff consumption, gift to the needy and some were accounted for as waste. Measuring the output level, the result showed that 38.3% of the respondents reported a very high level of output production, 49.2% agreed that their output level was high, 10% of the respondents reported a low output level and 2.5% said their output level was very low. The result showed that 87.5% of the respondents produced at a high rate which shows a good performance from the bakery owners/managers. This follows the opinion that the market for bread in Nigeria is very large due to the country's large population of over 220 million people. Akobundu (2006) forecast that with increasing population and craving for fast and convenient food, bread consumption will greatly increase in the society.

Furthermore, staff strength of the bakeries in the last three years was measured to know the performance of the bakery industry in Table 3. The result from the field shows that about 85% of the respondents employed between 1-5 labourers on a full-time basis while about 14% employed between 6-10 staffs on a full-time basis. The result went further to show that about 65% of the respondents employed between one and five staff on both full time and part time basis while 34.1% employed more than five staff but not more than ten staff on both part time and full-time basis.

From the survey, it was further gathered that 35.8% of the respondents believed that their staff strength (both full-time and part-time) was increasing compared to just 16% of the respondents who believed that their staff strength was decreasing. Although, 30% of the respondents believed that their own staff strength was fluctuating. This might be as a result of mobility of labour caused by several factors such as education and training, outlook or urge of the staff to rise or progress in life, peace and security etc. Meanwhile, a minority (17%) of the respondents believed that their staff strengths have been stagnant for the past three years.

From the study, it showed that the number of staff employed by the baking factories has increased compared to when they started. At the beginning, majority of the respondents pointed out the fact that they began the business alone and partly with the help of family members who came around to lend a helping hand in production. This is because there were not enough resources at the start to employ staff, but today, many of them are able to employ more staff for production, packaging and marketing of bread.

Table 3: Staff Strength Profile of Bakery Companies

Staff strength	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Number of full time employees available		
1-5	103	85.8
6-10	17	14.2
Number of part time employees		
1-5	78	65.9
6-10	42	34.1
Staff strength (full time and part time)		
Fluctuating	36	30.0
Stagnant	21	17.5
Decreasing	20	16.7
Increasing	43	35.8

Forms of technology alliances in the bakery industry

Table 4 measured the forms of technology alliances in the industry. This is done so as to know the type of technology alliances which the bakeries practice. The result shows that the bakers aligned with suppliers of raw materials and 41.7% of the respondents had a good relationship with their suppliers of raw materials, 11.7% of the respondents said they had alliance with their customers, 27.5% reported that they engaged in technical alliance with entities outside the supply chain, while 2.5% reported that they formed alliance with their direct competitor.

Furthermore, to buttress the forms of technology alliance, the study measured the alliance relationship with people of related business in Table 5 and the result shows that 83.3% of the respondents aligned with people of related business while 16.7% do not have interest in alliance with people of related business. This might be because they believed the alliance was not significant for their performance. Sullivan and Marvel (2011) reported that entrepreneurs who relied on more numerous collaborations for relevant business purposes should be better positioned to accurately and efficiently use their knowledge sets as they develop their venture.

Table 4: Collaboration Profile

Forms of collaborations	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
With suppliers of raw material	50	41.7
Collaboration with customers	14	11.7
Alliance with Entities outside the supply chain	33	27.5
Alliance with Competitors	3	2.5

The study went further to establish how the alliance started. To measure this, the following items were considered: alliance through special invitation, alliance through personal interest, compulsory alliance, alliance through business association and alliance with suppliers of raw materials. The result revealed that none of the respondents entered into any form of technology alliance through special invitation. Also, about 5% of the respondents said the alliance that they were into, was as a result of personal interest and not that they were compelled to do so. Therefore, they believed they were in a position to walk out of the alliance whenever they felt like doing so. About 48% of the respondents belonged to the bread bakers' association in their various towns and state at large. Also, about 22% of the respondents started alliance with suppliers of raw material because they believed this would give them the required edge in getting raw materials needed for production at a cheaper rate and when needed. Technology alliances with suppliers were often related to firms' improved efficiency of research and development activities and process improvements aimed at further cost reductions and heightened product quality (Aschhoff and Schmidt, 2008).

The study went further to establish whether respondents believed in firms' alliance with competitors. The results show that the majority of the respondents at 77.5% believed that their business would benefit from alliance with a competitor. Competitors, may for example, form alliances to acquire new skills from their alliance partners, build a better understanding of the competitor's behaviour, and enhance their competitive position. While the danger of learning races, where one partner acquired the skills of the other partner and then leave the alliance, is quite real in competitor alliances (Khanna *et al.*, 1994).

The result further affirmed that the majority of the respondents have not been visited by extension agents in the last one year. This is evident by the fact that only 26.7% of the respondents said they had received an extension agent at their factory, while 73.3% of the respondents said they had not received any extension agent. Furthermore, of the 26% that had extension agents at their factories, only about 8.3% said they had received them more than once, while about 91% said they had only received them once.

Table 5: Collaboration Profile of Respondents

Collaboration profile	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Do you have collaboration with people of related business		
Yes	100	83.3
No	20	16.7
If yes, how did the collaboration start		
Through special invitation	0	0
Personal interest	7	5.8
It is compulsory	7	5.8
Business association	58	48.4
Suppliers of raw materials	27	22.5
Do you think collaboration with competitors is necessary		
Yes	93	77.5
No	27	22.5
Have you been visited by an extension agent		
Yes	32	26.7
No	88	73.3
If yes, how many times		
Once	24	20.0
Twice	10	8.3
Yes	44	36.7
No	76	63.3

If yes, which organization conducted the training		
School	51	42.5
Vocation	12	10.0
Online	3	2.5
Bakery	54	45.0
Was the training beneficial to you		
Not beneficial	2.0	1.7
Somehow beneficial	16	13.3
Beneficial	33	27.5
Very beneficial	69	57.5

The impact of business knowledge cannot be overemphasized in the successful operation of a business venture. In view of this, the study sought to know how the respondents in the study area acquired skills and other technical know-how as regards the business. The result shows that 63.3% had gone through training in bread baking while 36.7% did not train in bread baking. Of the 120 respondents in the sample area, 45% underwent training in a bakery before establishing their own, while 42.5% of the respondents said they got trained in school while 2.5% of the respondents got trained online via YouTube videos, online baking classes and 10% went through vocational education to learn the art of baking.

According to Sullivan and Marvel (2011), knowledge of business possessed by an entrepreneur may lead to a desirable outcome like employing workers during the early stages of venture development and further notes that if a person has knowledge across business functions, there is a high chance of being able to optimize aspects of business-like cost minimization and profit maximization. Accordingly, the respondents reported that the training and knowledge they acquired had been very useful in the day-to-day running and management of their businesses. This is backed up by the fact that 57.5% of the respondents reported that the training had been very helpful, 27.5% believe the training had been beneficial, 13.3% said it was somehow beneficial while minority (1.7%) believed the training had not helped them at all.

Methods of solving operational problems

The study also measured the aspect of how respondents tried to solve technical operational issues that they encountered in the process of running their bakery business. From the result in Table 6, it can be seen that various methods or ways were available to the bakery owners to solve operational issues. About 35% of the respondents said they frequently called on colleagues within the industry to help out with operational issues, 54% of the respondents said they sometimes

Table 6: Respondents' Methods of Resolving Operational Problems

Resolving operational problems	Frequently n (%)	Sometimes n (%)	Not at all n (%)
Contact colleagues within the industry for assistance	43(35.8)	65(54.2)	12(10.0)
Commission outside experts/consultants	20(16.7)	41(34.2)	59(49.2)
Contact colleagues within the industry for assistance	27(22.5)	-----	93(77.5)
Consult with elders, aged and experience people around or at the family level	49(40.8)	59(49.2)	12(10.0)
Tried to solve it through research/personal efforts	37(30.8)	56(46.7)	27(22.5)
Through government support assistance	24(20.0)	42(35.0)	54(45.0)
Assisted by technical/business partners	36(30.0)	61(50.8)	23(19.2)
Hold periodic meetings to share information, experiences to solve technical problems	43(35.8)	68(56.7)	9(7.5)

Keys: *n* = frequency, % = percentage

called on colleagues within the industry, while a minority (10%) said they did not fancy calling on their colleagues for help. The result clearly shows that 90% of the respondents did form alliances with each other when it came to resolving operational issues. Competitors or firms from the same sector often have similar processes and thus, might offer valuable input for the development of new or improved production processes (Aschhoff and Schmidt, 2008).

Also, 16.7% of the respondents frequently engaged outside experts to solve operational issues for them, 24.2% of the respondents said they sometimes employed the services of external experts after they had exhausted the options of contacting colleagues within the industry, while 49.2% of the respondents said they did not even bother to look beyond the industry for solution to operational issues.

The study investigated the relationship between the bakery industry and universities/research institutes. Results show a very weak link between the industry and research institutions. This is evident from the fact that only 22.5% of the respondents said they had called on the expertise of research institutions to solve operational issues, none of the respondents said they sometimes requested the services of experts in the research institutions available to them, while 77.5% of the

respondents reported that they had never engaged the services of the research institutions. As stated by Caloghirou *et al.* (2003), universities and research institutions are widely considered to be important sources of new scientific and technological knowledge.

Furthermore, Table 6 shows that 40.8% of the respondents had tried to solve operational issues through consultations with elders and experienced people in the family and industry, 49.2% sometimes consulted with elders and experienced people around, while just 10% did not consult with elders and experienced people around. The result supports earlier arguments that most respondents started their baking business by involving family members and using family resources.

The Table also reveals that 30.8% frequently solved problems through personal efforts and research, 46.7% of the respondents sometimes relied on their own efforts and personal research, while 22.5% would rather look for experts or someone more knowledgeable rather than try things on their own.

Meanwhile, the study revealed that 45% of the respondents had never benefited from the support and assistance of the government, while 35% of the respondents said they sometimes benefitted from the support and the assistance of the government. 20% of the respondents reported that they benefited from the support and assistance of the government. Also, while 50% of the respondents sometimes sought the help of technical/business partners, 30% of the respondents frequently employed this option, while 19.2% of the respondents did not solve operational issues by calling on business and technical partners. The study further revealed that 35.8% of the bakeries did find their way around operational problems by engaging each other and sharing information during periodic meetings of the group, while 56.7% of the respondents sometimes relied on this pathway too. Meanwhile, 7.5% of the respondents did not adopt this method.

Table 7 shows the benefits of technology alliance, and the result revealed that majority (78%) of the respondents agreed that technology alliance provided easy access to information needed for better business performance, while 15% agreed to the fact that easy access to business related information could be beneficial if bakeries went into alliances. This is reaffirmed by Barr (2000) that a network of business-related contacts positively contributes to technical information flow among enterprises. Also, 2.5% of the respondents were indifferent to the proposition, while 4.2% of the bakers disagreed. More so, the table shows that engaging in technology alliance enhances the financial capabilities of the bakeries. This is evident from the fact that of the 120 respondents, 62% agreed that financial capabilities increase through engaging in technology alliance while 31% strongly agreed to the proposition. Although, 4.2% of the respondents disagreed while 17% were indifferent to the statement.

The Table reveals that technology alliance leads to efficient utilization of resources. This statement is supported by the majority (69%) of the bakery owners in the study who agreed to the proposition, 20% of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement while 1.7% were indifferent. This is followed by 4.2% who disagreed and 5% who strongly disagreed that technology alliance will lead to efficient utilization of resources. Furthermore, the majority (52%) of the respondents in Table 7 agreed that bakers entering into technology partnerships will strengthen their bargaining power, followed by 32% who strongly agreed with the statement. 5.8% are indifferent, 5% disagree and 4.2% strongly disagree. Therefore, the gains and benefit that come from technology alliance must definitely and ultimately translate to improved performances. However, the benefits must include cost minimization, profit maximization, creation of new opportunities and additional capabilities.

Table 7: Benefits of Technology Alliance

Benefits of Technology alliance	SA	A	I	SD	D
	n (%)				
It provides easy access to information	18(15.)	94(78.)	3(2.5)	---	5(4.2)
It increases financial capability.	38(31.)	75(62.)	2(1.7)	---	5(4.2)
It ensures efficient use of resources	24(20.)	83(69.)	2(1.7)	6(5.0)	5(4.2)
It strengthens bargaining power	39(32)	63(52.)	7(5.8)	5(4.2)	6(5.0)
It gives access to required resources	34(28.)	60(50.)	9(7.5)	13(10.)	4(3.3)
It increases the level of competitive strength	27(22.)	67(55.)	17(14.)	7(5.8)	2(1.7)
Lower opportunity cost	34(28.)	51(42.)	18(15.)	13(10.)	4(3.3)
It allows individuals to work in any of their member's workshop freely	39(32.)	49(40.)	12(10.)	11(9.2)	9(7.5)
It leads to an increase in sales	42(35.)	49(40.)	7(5.8)	17(14.)	5(4.2)
It creates barrier for new entrants	42(35.)	55(45.)	10(8.3)	9(7.5)	4(3.3)

Keys: SA= Strongly Agree; A=Agree; I=Indifference; SD= Strongly Disagree; D=Disagree

n= frequency, %=percentage

The Table also shows that 28% and 50% of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed, respectively, that technology alliance gave access to required resources needed to enhance performance, while about 8% of the respondents were indifferent, 10% of the respondents strongly disagreed and 3.3% of them simply disagreed.

The study inquired on the rate at which the respondents believed that competitive strength of the bakeries could be enhanced by going into alliance. The results show that 22% of the respondents strongly agreed, 55% agreed and this confirmed that over 70% of the respondents agreed that competitive strength of the bakeries could enhance alliance. While 5% strongly disagreed and 1.7% disagreed, only 14% remained indifferent to the proposition that technology alliance would determine the level of competitive strength. The Table further shows that 28% strongly agreed that technology alliance leads to lower comparative advantage (opportunity cost), 42% of the respondents agreed to this, 15% were indifferent, while 3.3% and 10% of the respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively.

Additionally, the study shows that 32% and 40% of the bakery owners strongly agreed and agreed, respectively, that technology alliance allows individuals to work freely in any member's place of work, 10% were indifferent to this idea, while 7.5% disagreed and 9.2% strongly disagreed. The Table further shows that technology alliance leads to increases in sales and this was strongly supported by 35% of the respondents as well as 40% who simply agreed to the statement. About 5% of the respondents were in between while 14% strongly disagreed. Meanwhile, a minority (4.2%) of the respondents disagreed.

The study also reveals that 35% and 45% of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed respectively that technology alliance would create an entry barrier for new entrants into the industry while 3.3% and 7.5% strongly disagreed and disagreed, respectively. Moreover, 8.3% of the respondents were indifferent to the idea that technology alliance would prevent new entrants into the industry.

Effect of Technology Alliances on Performance of the Bakery Industry

Hypothesis Testing

H_0 = supplier alliance has no significant effect on bakery performance

H_1 = supplier alliance has significant effect on bakery performance

(i) *Regression Analysis*: Table 8 is the result of the model summary of regression analysis showing the effect of technology alliance on performance of the bakery industry. The value of R (0.851) shows the correlation of the independent variable with the dependent variable. R Square ($R^2 = 0.724$) is the coefficient of determination. It means that about 72.4% of the variation in bakery performance can be explained by technology alliance. The value of R Squared is close to 1, meaning that the technology alliance can be used to determine the performance of the bakery industry.

(ii) *ANOVA*: Table 9 shows the Analysis of Variation (ANOVA) outcome with F value = 1.317, p -value = sig value = 0.026 which is less than 0.05 ($p < 0.05$), the study then rejects null hypothesis and accepts alternative hypothesis. This can be explained that the predictor will be useful to assume a positive and significant effect on the performance of the bakery industry.

(iii) *Regression coefficients*: Table 10 shows regression coefficients. From this table, the study explained the effect of an independent variable with four items on the dependent variable. The value of B in the unstandardized coefficient are the coefficients that will be used to formulate the regression model. At t -test = -1.157, p value = 0.032 for supplier alliances. Since the p -value is less than 0.05, the study accepts an alternative hypothesis that supplier alliance has a significant effect on bakery performance.

In summary of Table 10, consumer alliance, T -test = - 0.533, p -value = 0.511. The p -value is greater than 0.05, therefore, consumer alliance as an item used to measure the effect of technology alliance on bakery performance is not significant at 5% level of significance. Likewise the outcome from Entities outside the supply while supplier alliance and competitors' alliance are significant at 5% level of significance.

Table 8: Regression analysis of effect of technology alliance on performance

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R square	Std. error of estimate
1	0.851	0.724	0.701	0.28982

Predictors: (Constant), Customer Alliance, Supplier Alliance, Alliance with Entities outside the supply chain, Competitor Alliance

Dependent variable: Sales Volume

Table 9: ANOVA

Model	Sum of squares	Df	Mean of squares	F	Sig
Regression	9.739	8	1.948	1.317	0.026
Residual	139.011	94	1.479		
Total	148.750	99			

Predictors: (Constant), Customer Alliance, Supplier Alliance, Alliance with Entities outside the supply chain, Competitor Alliance.

Dependent variable: sales volume

Table 10: Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized		Standardized	T	Sig.
	Coefficients				
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	5.224	1.04		5.025	0
Supplier Alliance	-0.056	0.467	-0.644	-1.157	0.032
Consumer Alliance	-0.748	0.141	-0.054	-0.533	0.511
Entities outside the supply	-0.963	0.125	-0.124	-2.013	0.415
Competitor Alliance	-0.044	0.096	-0.084	-0.334	0.038

5.0 Conclusion

The study concludes that two items are significant and two are not at 5% level of significance. Furthermore, 83.3% of the 120 respondents engaged in alliances with people of related business and most of the respondents were into alliance through their business group (48.4%) and not the fact that it was compulsory (5.8%). Many of the respondents (41.7%) had collaborations with a particular supplier of the raw materials they used in baking while the remaining had business arrangements with research institutes and sales agents. Few of the respondents (16.7%) engaged in technical alliance with people of related business. Also, equipment leasing type of alliance between the respondents is very low at 10.8%.

Based on the findings, it could be concluded that the indigenous bakeries in the study area entered into alliances with suppliers of raw materials, research institutes, people in related businesses and entities outside the supply chain. Furthermore, the alliances were very beneficial to the indigenous bakeries and led to minimization of cost, maximization of outputs, efficient productions and increase in sales of the enterprises.

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